

I-RIM 2024 workshop proposal

Workshop title

Trends and challenges in collaborative robotics: perception, motion planning and control

Organizers

- Dr. Lorenzo Scalerà, University of Udine, Italy
- Dr. Matteo Terreran, University of Padova, Italy
- Dr. Enrico Villagrossi, STIIMA-CNR, Milan, Italy

Format

The format of the workshop is based on invited talks and a final discussion.

Abstract

Nowadays, the applications of human-robot collaboration are increasing in several manufacturing sectors, unlocking new robotic solutions and enabling the safe sharing of workspace between human operators and robots. The primary challenge of collaborative robotics is to ensure safe, intuitive, responsive, and effective interactions during shared operations, especially when a physical contact between robots and human partners is engaged, both in the short and long term. Despite significant research efforts aimed at improving the reasoning, perception, planning, and control of robotic manipulators, industrial applications have not yet taken full advantage of these remarkable advancements. Reliability and effectiveness of solutions are still far from industrial requirements and research has to push further the state-of-the-art before a wide technological transfer to real production plants. While current perception systems allow for the accurate localization of objects and human operators in the working environment, further intelligent technologies are needed to anticipate worker actions and needs, or react flexibly to unexpected actions. This workshop aims to present trends and challenges in collaborative robotics, and to explore future prospects in this field, with particular focus on perception, task and motion planning, and control. Furthermore, notable results of recent research projects that seek to bridge the gap between industry and academia will be presented and discussed.

Keywords:

Collaborative robotics; perception; motion planning; control

Intended audience

The workshop is targeted to academics and professionals in robotics, perception, motion planning and control with a focus on human-robot collaboration. The number of expected participants is 30 people, and the workshop will be held in presence. The workshop will be advertised on relevant mailing lists.

Organization and schedule

The planned workshop duration is 90 minutes and will host 5 invited presentations followed by an open discussion. All speakers are confirmed. The tentative schedule is as follows:

Presenter	Title/activity	Duration
Lorenzo Scalera University of Udine Matteo Terreran University of Padova Enrico Villagrossi STIIMA-CNR	Introduction	5 mins
Stefano Ghidoni University of Padova	Perception systems for intuitive and effective human-robot collaboration	12 mins
Andrea Orlandini ISTC-CNR	Knowledge-based approaches to enhance Smart Manufacturing	12 mins
Renato Vidoni, Matteo Manzardo Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	Safe and adaptive industrial collaborative robotic applications: examples and case studies	12 mins
Alberto Gottardi IT+Robotics	Human-robot collaborative transportation of flexible materials	12 mins
Andrea Giusti Fraunhofer Italia Research, Bolzano	Configurable collaborative robotics applications in construction	12 mins
All	Open discussion	25 mins

The planning reserves adequate time (ideally 25 mins) at the end for discussion and debate.

Workshop outcomes

The final discussion will be one of the main outcomes of the workshop, where the audience can interact with the panel of speakers to discuss recent advances in robotics and AI, as well as the challenges and limitations that still need to be addressed. Images and recordings of the event can be made available after the event.